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Food Technology, Processing and Engineering

APPLICATION OF QuEChERS IN DETERMINATION OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERNS IN SAMPLES OF SUGAR BEET AND SOIL

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Unregulated and not regularly monitored synthetic or natural chemicals that have a potentially or proven harmful effect on environmental and human health are classified as contaminants of emerging concern (CECs). CECs includes many different classes of compounds such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, illicit drugs, hormones, pesticides in current usage, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, micro- and nano-plastic, and many others. CECs can enter the environment from point sources with wastewater discharges as main ones and diffuse pollution sources such as terrestrial runoff from agricultural land. Fate of CECs in the environment is depends on their physical and chemical properties as well as of environmental conditions; transformation products of CECs additionally increase the complexity of environmental "CECs cocktails". Surface water represents the main recipient of wastewater discharges, so numerous CECs can be further transferred to agricultural soils if surface water is used for irrigation. The presence of CECs in agricultural lands has led to increased concern about the potential to accumulate in plants because of their tendency to uptake chemicals present in the soil. This leads to the introduction of pollutants into the food chain with potentially harmful effects during acute and chronic human exposure through food consumption. The aim of this work is to determine the efficiency of sample preparation methods based on QuEChERS extraction for the investigation of the CECs levels in sugar beet root. This method previously showed a good efficiency when applied to soil samples. The method was applied for the determination of CECs in spiked and real samples of sugar beet root, as well in real samples of soil. The content of CECs in water used for irrigation was also determined applying another sample preparation method based on solid-phase extraction. All samples were analyzed by high- performance liquid chromatography coupled with triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Keywords: contaminants of emerging concern, sugar beet, soil, surface water, high performance liquid chromatography

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